

GOLDBACH'S BINARY CONJECTURE. AN INDUCTIVE APPROACH

(MSC classes: 11P32, 11U99)

Daniele Bertaggia

October 20, 2024

Abstract

In this work the author wants to show how every even number greater than 4 can be written as the sum of two odd prime numbers, possibly equals. Evidence of the properties of natural numbers is often based on the use of a test method called induction.

In particular, the technique used in this research is that of strong induction (or principle of induction on the course of values).

It is necessary to underline that the induction principle is often used to prove properties concerning natural numbers and it should be noted that it has a confirmatory and demonstrative character of a property provided that this is already conjectured through the experimentation of several consecutive cases.

This method often uses an intermediate property.

Finally, the author believes that the noteworthy results that emerged in this research is essentially the Goldbach's binary conjecture demonstration by strong induction.

1 Introduction

In 1742, the Prussian mathematician Christian Goldbach wrote a letter to Euler in which he proposed the following conjecture:

Any integer greater than 5 can be written as the sum of three prime numbers.

Euler, taking an interest in the problem, replied by reformulating the problem in the following equivalent version:

Any even number greater than 2 can be written as the sum of two prime numbers.

Euler's version is the form in which the conjecture is currently formulated and is sometimes also referred to as the strong Goldbach conjecture. Goldbach's weak conjecture, which is implied by the strong conjecture, asserts that all odd numbers greater than 5 can be written as the sum of three primes.

The principle of mathematical induction says that to prove that all natural numbers enjoy the property P it is sufficient to prove two things, that:

- 1) the number 0 enjoys P, (basis of induction)
- 2) for every n, if all numbers less than or equal to n enjoy P, also n+1 enjoys it (induction step).

When the base is greater than 0, we are in the presence of a induction's translation.

In the strong induction the induction step is demonstrated through the following three steps:

- 2.(a) we consider a generic k;
- 2.(b) it is assumed that the property P holds for 0, 1, 2, ..., k, (induction hypothesis);
- 2.(c) it is proved that the property P holds for k+1.

At this point it is important to note that in the works of H. A. Helfgott (2013)^{[4][5]} actually significant steps are taken relating to the Goldbach's weak conjecture (from which binary conjectures cannot be demonstrated) while, in this work, the author believes he has demonstrated the Goldbach's binary conjecture which implies, in turn, the demonstration of weak conjecture.

2 Goldbach's binary conjecture demonstration by strong induction

We want to prove the following property $G(k)$:

$$\forall k > 4 \exists p_{k-1}, q_{k-1} \in P \setminus \{2\} \mid 2k = p_{k-1} + q_{k-1} + 2 \quad k \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

$$p_{k-1} < q_{k-1}$$

Proof. We call the following proposition indistinctly property $G'(k)$ or property G' :

$$\forall k > 3 \exists p_k, q_k \in P \setminus \{2\} \mid 2k = p_k + q_k \quad k \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

$$p_k < q_k$$

from which:

$$G(k+1) = G'(k) + 2$$

and

$$G'(k) \Rightarrow G(k+1)$$

1. $k = 4$ (Base)

$G'(4)$ holds in fact:

$$2 * 4 = 8 = 3 + 5$$

with:

$$G(4+1) = G'(4) + 2 = G(5)$$

$$G'(4) \Rightarrow G(5) \text{ where } 5 \text{ is Base of } G(k)$$

infact: $2*5 = 10 = 8 + 2 = 3 + 5 + 2$

2.(a) Let $k = x$, for a generic natural number k greater than 4. (Step)

2.(b) Suppose that $G'(4), G'(5), G'(6), \dots, G'(x)$ (Ip. of induction)

We have that:

$$G'(4) \Rightarrow G(5)$$

$$G'(5) \Rightarrow G(6)$$

$$G'(6) \Rightarrow G(7)$$

...

$$G'(x - 1) \Rightarrow G(x)$$

Now we consider $(x+1)$, we have two cases:

$$i) 2x = p_x + (p_x + 2)$$

with $p_x, (p_x + 2)$ twin primes

and:

$$p_x = x - 1$$

$$(p_x + 2) = x + 1$$

then trivially we have $G(x+1)$;

ii) $(x - 1), (x + 1)$ not twin primes

but for 2.(b) we have:

$$G(x + 1) = G'(x) + 2$$

$$G'(x) \Rightarrow G(x + 1)$$

In both cases i) and ii) we have $G(x)$ (Ip. of induction) and $G(x+1)$ and for this finally we can say that $G(k)$ holds for every k greater than 4. (For this see also the Structural induction definition in [1], [6]).

□

3 Observations 1

With the same procedure it is possible to prove the conjecture on the infinity of the prime twin numbers.

4 Observations 2

These five principles are equivalent to each other:

- Principle of induction (simple)
- Principle of minimum
- Principle of strong induction
- Principle of simple structural induction
- Principle of structural induction

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Author's information:

Company: KUKA Roboter Italy (external collaborator)

Company address: Via Leonardo Da Vinci, 3, 10095 Grugliasco (TO)

Mailing address: Via Rivalta, 14, 10090 Bruino (TO)

Email address: daniele.bertaggia74@gmail.com